

Acoustical and Flow Behaviour Analysis of Various Muffler Designs through CFD Analysis- A Critical Review

Rahul Kumar Mishra¹, Prof. Amit Kumar Asthana²

1. Research Scholar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Truba Institute of Engineering and Information Technology, Bhopal (MP)
2. Head, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Truba Institute of Engineering and Information Technology, Bhopal (MP)

Abstract: Mufflers are installed within the exhaust system of most internal combustion engines, although the muffler is not designed to serve any primary exhaust function. The muffler is engineered as an acoustic soundproofing device designed to reduce the loudness of the sound pressure created by the engine by way of acoustic quieting. The majority of the sound pressure produced by the engine is emanated out of the vehicle using the same piping used by the silent exhaust gases absorbed by a series of passages and chambers lined with roving Fiberglass insulation and/or resonating chambers harmonically tuned to cause destructive interference wherein opposite sound waves cancel each other out an unavoidable side effect of muffler use is an increase of back pressure which decreases engine efficiency. Current paper presents a critical review of current state of the art regarding the research field chosen for study.

Keywords: Mufflers, exhaust system, IC Engines, sound pressure, Fiberglass insulation

I. Introduction

Automobile engineering is the one of the streams of mechanical engineering. It deals with the various types of automobiles, their mechanism of transmission systems and its applications. Automobiles are the different types of vehicles used for transportation of passengers, goods, etc. Basically, all the types of vehicles work on the principle of internal combustion processes Different types of fuels are burnt inside the cylinder at higher temperature to get the transmission motion in the vehicles Therefore, every mechanical and automobile engineer should have the knowledge of automobile its mechanism and its various applications.

The exhaust system quiets the noise produced during engine operation and routes engine exhaust gases to the rear of the vehicle body. Trace the flow of exhaust gases from the engine exhaust manifold to the tailpipe Learn the names of the parts. Various emission control systems are used to reduce the amount of toxic (poisonous) substances produced by an engine. Some systems prevent fuel vapors from entering the atmosphere (air surrounding the earth). Other emission control systems remove unburned and partially burned fuel from the engine exhaust.

The emissions from millions of vehicles add up. These emissions are by products from the engine combustion process and from the evaporation of fuel. Despite the ever-growing number of vehicles on the road, studies show that ten to thirty percent of vehicles cause the majority no vehicle-related air pollution.

A typical exhaust system comprises of a combination of metallic pipes for carrying out the toxic emissions released by the combustion of gases, more often from auto engines. The efficient working of an exhaust is essentially needed for the safe and reliable running of vehicles. The latest exhaust systems are designed to clean the gases before throwing them out in the atmosphere. Modified systems facilitate a smoother flow of gases, and thus enhance the efficiency of engines.

When the flow of exhaust gases from the engine to the

atmosphere is obstructed to any degree, back pressure arises and the engine's efficiency, and therefore power, is reduced Performance- oriented mufflers and exhaust systems thus strive to minimize back pressure by Employing numerous technologies and methods to attenuate the sound. For the majority of such systems, however, the general rule of more power, more noise applies.

Several such exhaust systems that utilize various designs and construction methods: Vector muffler: for larger diesel trucks, uses many concentric cones, or for performance automotive applications, using angled baffles to cause exhaust impulses to cancel each other out.

The first muffler was patented in 1897 by Marshall and Milton Reeves. The muffler is the main component of the exhaust system for silencing acoustic exhaust noises. There are many different designs of mufflers available today. Some being chambered, glass pack, straight through glass packs and combinations of those. It is designed to reduce loudness acoustic sound pressures created by the combustion process. Fiberglass is the most commonly used material inside of traditional mufflers. Other materials could include rock minerals, wool, fiber mat, or simple metal chambers to aid in absorption and reduce unwanted exhaust sounds.

A muffler must be able to withstand the running conditions of a vehicle. This includes the engine sound frequencies, hazardous driving conditions (off- roading), and most of the muffler must withstand rust and corrosion.

II. Literature Review

Amit Kumar Gupta et. al. Mufflers are device which are installed within the exhaust system. It is basically used for noise reduction. Reactive muffler plays an important role as noise control element for reduction of automotive exhaust noise, fan noise, and other noise sources involving the flow of gases. Mufflers are typically arranged along the exhaust pipe as the part of the exhaust system of an internal combustion engine to reduce its noise. The expansion

chambers with various cross section like Circular, Elliptical, Square & Rectangular are commonly used for noise attenuation. The degree of attenuation can also be improved with design optimization of inlet pipes, outlet pipes & baffle plates. The present paper aims to concentrate to study the acoustic performance of reactive mufflers with various cross sections by one-dimensional wave approach. Here the result shows to identify the transmission loss characteristics by taking different cross sections of simple expansion chambers by taking consideration of constant volume of expansion chamber.

Ayush Lal et. al. considered CFD Analysis of Flow through Muffler to Select Optimum Muffler Model for CI Engine Mufflers increase the pressure of the exhaust gases (back pressure) thereby reducing the sound levels of the same. Therefore, importance is given to muffler designing and a particular design is selected for which the sound reduction is maximum. for this exhaust gas CFD simulation is carried in software's such as ANSYS FLUENT. Two muffler designs have been modelled and CFD gas flow simulation has been carried in both of them. Based upon the gas flow through them, on comparison we have selected the optimum model. Demonstrates that model is more efficient for noise reduction and other design offers more reduction in gas pressure and hence reduces noise levels.

Balraj D. Kawade et. al. discussed on Design alternatives for automobile silencer. The exhaust gases coming out from engine are at very high speed and temperature. Silencer has to reduce noise, vibrations. While doing so it is subjected to thermal, vibration and fatigue failures which cause cracks. So, it is necessary to analyze the Vibrations which would further help to pursue future projects to minimize cracks, improving life and efficiency of silencer. For silencer vibration analysis we can use FEM simulation methodology described as a better solution over conventional trial and error method for predicting the errors in modal analysis. Natural frequencies can be determined and the mode shapes can be reviewed in the light of its performance contributing to any increased like hood of undesired trends.

Prof. Bharat S. Patel et. al. The purpose of this paper is to present Air pollution generated from mobile sources is a problem of general interest. Vehicle population is projected to grow close to 1300 million by the year 2030. Due to incomplete combustion in the engine, there are a number of incomplete combustion products CO, HC, NO_x, particulate matters etc. This review paper discusses automotive exhaust emissions and its impact, automotive exhaust emission control by platinum (noble) group metal-based catalyst in catalytic converter, history of catalytic convertor, types of catalytic convertor, limitation of catalytic convertor and also achievements of catalytic convertor.

Jayashri P. Chaudhari et. al. considering different noise parameters produced by the engine. Here different design parameters with ammonia pulsator have been considered to improve the efficiency & emission control of the absorptive muffler. Considering different noise parameters produced by the engine. Here different design parameters with ammonia pulsator have been considered to improve the efficiency & emission control of the absorptive muffler. His Aim is to design, develop and analysis of mathematical

modelling and derivation of dimensional parameters of absorptive muffler with ammonia pulsator using UG NX-8.0 and ANSYS workbench. The formulated muffler traditional design problem will be solved by new design and optimization.

M. Rajasekhar Reddy et. al. The present work aims at improve the frequency of NSD (Nash Shell Damper) muffler by controlling the noise level of a diesel engine by developing an exhaust muffler for the same, since exhaust noise is the single largest contributor to the overall noise from the engine.

The TATA INDICA TURBOMAX TDI BSIV four-cylinder diesel engine car was considered for test purposes. In this study Muffler dimensions are measured through the Benchmarking, to create CAD models. The CAD models are created in CATIA V5 R19, later these CAD models of muffler are exported to HYPER MESH for pre-processing work. Free analysis is carried out on this muffler by FEA Method using NASTRAN Software.

Munjal, M.L. et. al. explained Recent Advances in Muffler Acoustic, Challenges for muffler design has been constraints on size, back pressure, and, of course, the cost. Designing for sufficient insertion loss at the engine firing frequency and the first few harmonics has been the biggest challenge. Breakthroughs have been achieved in the prediction and control of breakout noise from the elliptical and circular muffler shell as well as the end plates of typical mufflers. Diesel particulate filters and inlet air cleaners have also been modelled acoustically.

Rahul D. Nazirkar et. al. improved the design efficiency of muffler, resonating of the exhaust muffler should be avoided by its natural frequency. The solid modelling of exhaust muffler is created by CATIA-V5 and modal analysis is carried out by ANSYS to study the vibration and natural frequency of muffler. So as to differentiate between the working frequency from natural frequency and avoid resonating. By fixing the muffler at first and double expansion chamber we can increase the frequency and avoid the resonance. Transmission loss of the muffler can be increased by adding protrusion pipe at inlet and outlet. It can be seen that the finite element modal analysis has certain significance in the study of vibration characteristics of the muffler.

S. Balamurugan et. al. designed a muffler for four stroke diesel engine In this research baffle arrangement is used to resist the flow of the exhaust from the engine. An exhaust pipe must be carefully designed to carry toxic and/or noxious gases away from the users of the machine Indoor generators and furnaces can quickly fill an enclosed space with carbon monoxide or other poisonous exhaust gases if they are not properly vented to the outdoors. Also, the gases from most types of machines are very hot, the pipe must be heat resistant and it must not pass through or near anything that can burn or damaged by the heat by using this kind of muffler we can eliminate the enormous amount of toxic exhaust that are all released from an engine which leads the way towards the eco-friendly vehicle production. It reduces the usage of fuel about 0.5%, also reduces the back pressure of the exhaust flow, and thus increases the range of continuous exhaust flow thana normal conventional engine.

Mr. Sanchit Babarao Dhotre et. al. describes various exhaust noises, vibration and their contribution. Frequency,

vibration and noise technique is studied through energy flow. Hence, it is necessary to study the behaviour of muffler by analyzing the vibration modes and vibration response. They conclude that the natural frequency of existing model is much lower and this model of muffler silencer are unable to sustain the resonance which are formed due to noise and also jerk comes from road and this causes vibration in silencer which is un comfort to ride. But by making modification in muffler silencer the natural frequency at different modes is greater than existing and this frequency is capable to reduce vibration and it provide comfort ride and efficient ride.

Sandeep G Thorat et. al. analyzed with respect to both acoustics and back pressure. As per the various studies reactive mufflers with extended inlet and outlet pipes into muffler, which is not present in current design can significantly reduce the noise level. Helmholtz resonator can also be introduced to cancel the noise of dominating frequencies. Also, a sound absorbing material like glass fibres and steel wool can be incorporated for better results. The new muffler design would be a 3-chamber muffler with extended perforated tube. Further it would have a resonator to damp the most dominating frequencies. The total length of the silencer may be reduced to make it more cost effective.

Shital Shah et. al. Exhaust noise from engines is one of component noise pollution to the environment. Exhaust systems are developed to attenuate noise meeting required db (a) levels and sound quality, emissions based on environment norms. Most of the advances in theory of acoustic filters and exhaust mufflers have been developed in last two decades. This paper deals with a practical approach to design, develop and test muffler particularly reactive muffler for exhaust system, which will give advantages over the conventional method with shorten product development cycle time and validation. This paper also emphasis on how modern CAE tools could be leveraged for optimising the overall system design balancing conflicting requirements like Noise & Back pressure.

Suyog S. Mane et. al. The present study describes the analysis of back pressure of the muffler by using CFD simulation. The CFD analysis is done to avoid the tedious experimentation. The flow simulation is carried out using k- ϵ turbulent model as it is most suitable for turbulent flows having less converging time. Total four cases were analyzed including the base model muffler. Thus, three modifications were done in muffler geometry. The modification with reduced baffle spacing produced least back pressure with reduction in back pressure by 9.60%.

Baruah, S., Chatterjee et. al. In this work, an elliptical chamber muffler model of a MAHINDRA C.I. engine is studied based on CFD analysis of the exhaust gas flow through the muffler chamber. Two designs for the aforementioned muffler are analyzed one of which consists of perforated inlet, outlet and central pipes which, if implemented in actual practice could bring about better and improved sound attenuation. Transmission loss is calculated for both the muffler models based on pressure distribution obtained from CFD analysis results. Comparative study of the two muffler models, one without the presence of any perforation and the other after

incorporation of perforation, is carried out in ANSYS FLUENT 14.5.

Ujjal Kalita et. al. concentrated on Different sound absorption materials that are currently used for noise reduction Different components are present in the muffler for transmission loss like perforated tubes, absorption materials etc. by which noise is reduced. The production of metal foams, ceramic foams, and aerogels can contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, their practical use in transportation will help in reducing other emissions and help in reducing fuel consumption. Since these materials possess high structural strength and reduced structural weight simultaneously, their use in the aerospace and automotive industries has the potential to reduce fuel consumption and save energy.

Manimaran, R et. al. In this work, exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) is varied in a direct injection constant speed diesel engine using extended coherent flame model for 3-zones by CFD. The three zones are unmixed fuel zone, mixed gases zone, unmixed air plus EGR zone. The three zones are too small to be resolved by the mesh and are therefore modelled as sub-grid quantities. The mixed zone is the result of turbulent and molecular mixing between gases in the other two zones, where combustion takes place. Grid and time independent tests are carried out further to find the appropriate space and time steps respectively. The preliminary studies are carried out to validate the model with the experiments. The present study is conducted towards varying the EGR in the cylinder. CFD results indicate that as EGR increases, nitrogen oxides decrease in a general trend observed in diesel engines. The predicted model shows that flame temperature is lowered in the combustion chamber with the increase in EGR. However, as oxides of nitrogen decreases, soot increases due to lowered oxygen concentration. Reaction variable and temperature contours in the cylinder reveal that combustion regresses as EGR is increased.

Pradyumna Saripalli et. al. The exhaust pollution has become one of the important problems of environment pollution with applications in automobile industry, and the exhausted muffler has been paid attention to improve the performance of engines. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method was used to explore the aerodynamic performance of the muffler. Resistance muffler research relates with the fields of acoustics, fluid dynamics, heat transfer and mechanism design. The project report simulates the field by numerical method with Cosmos Flow and analyses the effect which the internal flow field has on the performance of the muffler. With this method the pressure distribution in the muffler is simulated and the pressure loss is predicted for the structure modification. The experiment results verify that the assembly performance of the muffler modified is better than the original muffler.

Kashyap Chowdary et. al. As major limitation of diesel engines is the high soot and nitrogen oxide emissions which cannot be reduced totally with only conventional catalytic converters today, varying fuel characteristics became a focus of interest to meet the pollution emission legislations as they require very few or no changes in existing engine model. The present work deals with, numerical analysis of combined effect of Advanced Start of Injection (SOI) and

Exhaust Gas Re-circulation (EGR) on performance and emissions which were studied, by performing numerical analysis on a Caterpillar 3401 single cylinder C.I engine model at constant speed using diesel as fuel via three-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) procedures and validated with experimental data. The SOI is advanced from 11° Crank angle bTDC to 14.5° Crank angle bTDC and EGR as a fraction is increased from 0% to 10%. The modified conditions of these parameters resulted in simultaneous reduction of NO_x and Soot.

Shinde, P.V et. al. The acoustic attenuation and acoustic pressure levels of a single-cylinder diesel engine are computed using COMSOL Multiphysics tool to evaluate the performance of the reactive muffler. To increase the travel of exhaust gas, internal modifications in the geometry of the muffler has been done. The experimental analysis shows that the pressure drop for the new developed model is much lesser than that of the existing model for same conditions. CFD approach is employed to investigate the effect of flow velocity and temperature on the acoustic attenuation performances of both muffler models. The experimental and numerical results of transmission loss have been validated. The results of the numerical analysis show close agreement with the experimental results. It is observed that the backpressure of the new developed muffler faces 42% reduction. Increasing the volume of the muffler with a single perforated baffle plate leads to noise reduction of 5.5%. The new developed muffler has been used to study the effects of transmission loss, acoustic attenuation analysis and acoustic pressure levels for the low-frequency range.

Selvanathan et. al. Turbocharger is a major contributor of both power and volumetric efficiency in internal combustion engines. Turbocharger is driven by exhaust gases collected using an exhaust manifold. Therefore, the design of an exhaust manifold also plays an important role in improving the efficiency of the engine. Usually, various factors are involved in designing an exhaust manifold and a computerized optimization would reduce the numerous technical and cost factors involved. This paper aims to analyze the design of an exhaust manifold to establish the significance of various factors involved in designing an exhaust manifold by comparing various existing designs using Computational Fluid Dynamics.

Gajendra Raghuvanshi et. al. The exhaust manifold in an internal combustion engine is a very vital component affecting the performance of an engine. The engine's volumetric efficiency is directly depended on its ability to push out the exhaust gases effectively to suck in more air for combustion. To effectively expel the exhaust gases, a good manifold is required and in cases of a turbocharged engine the manifold is even more important. The objective of this project is to analyze existing designs of exhaust manifold to establish a better understanding of the significance of various factors involved in its design process. The material and specifications are varied and results were compared in present paper.

D Sunny Manohar et. al. This project goals in re-designing an exhaust manifold by means of determining the thermal stresses and deflections exhibited underneath various operating situations with distinctive materials and temperatures. The objective is to make certain the

suitability of the design for two different fabrics from the view point of reliability and serviceability. Defects in present manifold are cracks normally occur because of prolonged publicity to severe temperatures, defects in casting and repeated warmness cycling. Welded regions and the curved profiles are the essential regions of failure. A methodology is developed to ensure the best suited design and material for the given operating conditions; Manifold behaviour is analyzed on two different materials such as stainless steel and grey cast iron. Redesigning the curved profiles can reduce the turbulence effect of the exhaust gases on the welds. High-end CAD/CAM software such as SOLIDWORKS 2016 and ANSYS 16.0 are used for modelling and analysis. Exhaust manifold is design by using SolidWorks software and transfer to Ansys software, Computational fluid dynamic analysis is performed to study flow characteristics such as pressure velocity and temperature to study its performance and back pressure factors, and temperature after convection by surrounding air, than the same temperature after CFD analysis is applied on body in static structural analysis module to study its strength on thermal load that is to find out its stresses and deformation on working thermal load conditions, the material which give good strength to weight ratio will conclude the best material.

Cihan et. al. The exhaust manifold is an important component, although it appears to be simple among engine parts. The effective efficiency and performance of the engine affect many parameters such as the diameter, length, material and geometry of the exhaust manifold. In the study presented, commonly used two manifold designs were drawn in the SOLIDWORKS software. Then, these manifolds were transferred to the ABAQUS V6.13 software. The physical properties of gasoline, alcohol and LPG are used as fluid flow for each manifold. In the analysis, the pressure, velocity and temperature changes of the manifolds are determined at the measured points. Gasoline fluid is lower pressure and velocity than the other two fuels in the type A and type B exhaust manifold. The type A exhaust manifold compared to type B manifold; higher pressures have been reached in all three fuels. Therefore, the performance and efficiency of the engine can be increased with A type manifold.

Sandeep M Chauhan et. al. Now a days the global warming and air pollution are big issue in the world. The more amount of air pollution is due to emissions from an internal combustion engine. The exhaust pipe is an important part of IC engine. it's structure and performance have direct impact on the engine power, economy and emissions. Exhaust system plays a vital role in reducing harmful gases, but the presence of after treatment systems increases the exhaust back pressure. The back pressure at the exhaust port thus losing power, increasing fuel consumption and piston effort to exhaust the gases out. The substrate has been modelled as porous medium for analysis purpose. These models have been imported in CFD tool for analysis. After importing the CAD data inside the CFD software, with proper boundary conditions, the CFD analysis has been carried out. Based on the study, individual system contributions to the total pressure drop and flow uniformity have been analyzed and improvement

areas of the existing system for better flow uniformity have been suggested. The design is reasonable and can achieve the design goal.

P. Manikandan et. al. Exhaust manifold is one of the components of IC engine for improving the volumetric efficiency. The volumetric efficiency of the engine can be increased by reducing the backpressure in the exhaust manifold. This work analyses the flow through two different models of exhaust manifold using CFD. The analysis results of two models are compared for back pressure and velocity. By comparing the results of two models the decrease in back pressure is found which ensure improvement in volumetric efficiency of the engine.

Vignesh. G et. al. This paper describes how different parameters of the manifold, such as material type and geometric sizes, have an impact on the efficiency and performance of an automobile engine, and how they affect the efficiency and performance of the engine. Also, this paper explains how back pressure are often reduced by certain change within the geometry of the manifold.

At various points along the manifold, changes in pressure, velocity, and temperature were mathematically calculated. Generally speaking, engine exhaust backpressure refers to the force produced by engines to overcome hydraulic resistance in the exhaust system and release gases into the atmosphere.

A. Vinay Gopal et. al. Exhaust manifold is one of the most critical components of an IC Engine. The designing of exhaust manifold is a complex procedure and is dependent on many parameters viz. back pressure, exhaust velocity, mechanical efficiency etc. Preference for any of this parameter varies as per designer's needs. Usually fuel economy, emissions and power requirement are three different streams or thought regarding exhaust manifold design. In any multi-cylinder IC engine, an exhaust manifold (also known as a header) collects the exhaust gases from multiple cylinders into one pipe. This header is connected to these cylinders through bends. It is attached downstream of the engine and is major part in multi-cylinder engines where there are multiple exhaust streams that have to be collected into a single pipe. Exhaust gases come out of this Header as a single stream of hot exhaust gases through single outlet. This work comprehensively analyses eight different models of exhaust manifold and concludes the best possible design for least emissions and complete combustion of fuel to ensure least pollution. The main objective of this investigation is to design an exhaust manifold by using CATIA V5 R20 software and also find out pressures and velocities at various mass flow rates in the exhaust manifolds with Long Bend Side Exit (LBSE), Long Bend Middle Exit (LBME) and Reducer and find out the performance of the exhaust manifold with various modifications in its design or adding a component for the exhaust manifold to increase its effectiveness. In the current analysis mass flow rates considered in the exhaust manifold are 2 kg/s, 4 kg/s, 6 kg/s, 8 kg/s, 10 kg/s, 12 kg/s in all the various modification ns in the exhaust manifolds

Kanupriya Bajpai et. al. Exhaust manifold is one of the most critical components of an IC Engine. The functioning of exhaust manifold is complex and is dependent on many parameters viz. back pressure, exhaust velocity, scavenging

etc. In the present work, the performance of a four-stroke four-cylinder gasoline engine exhaust manifold have been analyzed using three different fuels - gasoline, alcohol, and LPG for the estimation of flow characteristics, thermal characteristics, and minimum back pressure. The manifold modelling is done in Creo2.0 followed by meshing and analysis in ANSYS. The LPG fuel gives minimum back pressure, temperature and velocity being approximately in the same range for all three fuels viz. gasoline, alcohol and LPG. Thus, LPG can be considered as a suitable alternative for gasoline in terms of minimum back flow in manifold.

K. S. Umesh et. al. Exhaust manifold is one of the most critical components of an IC Engine. The designing of exhaust manifold is a complex procedure and is dependent on many parameters viz. back pressure, exhaust velocity, mechanical efficiency etc. Preference for any of this parameter varies as per designer's needs. Usually fuel economy, emissions and power requirement are three different streams or thought regarding exhaust manifold design. This work comprehensively analyses eight different models of exhaust manifold and concludes the best possible design for least emissions and complete combustion of fuel to ensure least pollution.

Teja MA et. al. Overall engine performance of an engine can be obtained from the proper design of engine exhaust systems. With regard to stringent emission legislation in the automotive sector, there is a need design and develop suitable combustion chambers, inlet, and outlet manifold. Exhaust manifold is one of the important components which affect the engine performance. Flow through an exhaust manifold is time dependent with respect to crank angle position. In the present research work, numerical study on four-cylinder petrol engine with two exhaust manifolds running at constant speed of 2800 rpm was studied. Flow through an exhaust manifold is dependent on the time since crank angle positions vary with respect to time. Unsteady state simulation can predict how an intake manifold work under real conditions. The boundary conditions are no longer constant but vary with time. The main objectives that to be studied in this work is:

- To prepare the cad model in the CATIA software by using the actual parametric dimensions.
- To prepare finite element model in the computer aided analysis software by specifying the approximate element size for meshing.
- To find and calculate the actual theoretical values for the input boundary conditions.
- To study the flow patterns generated due to the flow of the exhaust gases from the manifold.
- To study the velocity and pressure distribution in ports at maximum flow rate.
- To study the static pressure, drop, total pressure drop, and energy loss in the flow pattern generated in the exhaust manifold.

Anker Katre et. al. The important function of a exhaust muffler is to route the exhaust gases from the engine exhaust manifold to the atmosphere while reducing the noise created and back-pressure. Noise reduction is an emerging concern in the automotive industry, and reduction in back-pressure enhances the fuel economy of the engine. In this Study comprehensively analyses two different

models of exhaust muffler and concludes the best possible design for lowest pressure drop. Backpressure is obtained with experimentally on both models. Back pressure was obtained based on the flow field analysis and was also compared with all muffler design. Virtual simulation for back-pressure testing is performed by Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) analysis using ANSYS CFD. Finite Element (FE) model generation of the muffler structure is performed using Ansys as the preprocessor. The structural mesh is modelled using 2D shell elements, wherein the internal tubes with fine perforated holes are considered. The CFD fluid meshing is done with tetra elements using Ansys Workbench as the CFD pre-processor.

L. Prabhu et. al. A Muffler is a gadget for lessening the measure of clamor produced by the fumes of an inner burning motor. Inner burning motors are commonly furnished with a fumes suppressor (Silencer) created by the ignition procedure to smother the acoustic beat. The direct cause of back pressure in the engine will be the stress and temperature of exhaust gases that flow through the silencer. To relieve the back pressure in the exhaust system, the engine power must be used. Execution of Muffler underneath different working state is typically acquired through design analysis. Accessibility of compressible flow execution parameters is limited, and trial testing can be cost restrictive. The mathematical fluid Dynamics analysis provides better results for this case. The ability to use analytical fluid components is a test to determine their suitability to determine the conditions of their display. The venture's goal is to examine the gases. gas stream attributes in the suppressor's current and modified structure. Our effort is to focus on enhancing the structure so that there is less back weight and silencer's expanded existence. The Computational Fluid elements investigation would be completed by utilizing CFD apparatus CFX. With parameters such as weight and temperature dissemination, disturbance power and liquid power at different load conditions, an extensive report would be done.

P.S.R Anil Teja et. al. Using diesel engines mostly as main power source has gained the importance in the recent years. Technical specification of the diesel engine and its components has been the main focus of the researchers. The muffler is defined as a device for reducing the amount of noise emitted by an engine. The muffler is engineered as an acoustic sound proofing device designed to reduce the loudness of the sound pressure created by the engine by way of Acoustic quieting. Due to increased environmental concerns requiring less noise emissions combined with reduced emission of harmful gases, it is becoming very crucial to carefully design the exhaust system mufflers for road transport application

C. Krishnara J et. al. The aim of the work is to analyze the performance of the engine exhaust manifold. Because the engine exhaust manifold is a significant factor in the engine performance. In this work the manifold design is prepared with the help of CAD software and it is analyzed by the ANSYS. This CFD and thermal analysis also done to check the performance of the redesigned exhaust manifold. The aim of CFD simulations performed to investigate the volumetric efficiency behaviour of an exhaust.

Nandkumar Patil et. al. details understanding for exhaust back pressure optimization of compression ignition (CI)

engine. Diesel engines having less operation cost due to this these are mostly used in commercial vehicles, now days fuel consumption and engine durability plays a vital role for the overall vehicle performance. Exhaust system main function is to through away burnt gases without any leakage from combustion chamber of engine to atmosphere. Optimization of exhaust system is crucial, to achieve higher engine power output, compact components packaging, tougher emission norms and less fuel consumption. CFD analysis is used to find out pressure variation pattern due to major exhaust system component placement in complete system. Back pressure of exhaust system is increased by muffler placement toward engine and reduces by muffler moving away from engine.

R Murali et. al. The exhaust system in any Internal Combustion (IC) engine is a critical component that affects the engine's performance. A poorly designed exhaust system generally results in an increment of exhaust backpressure. Backpressure is one of the fluid's characteristics that acts as a resistance to exhaust gas flow. Relatively higher backpressure blocks the exhaust gas flow from discharging efficiently, decreasing the engine's performance. In general, higher backpressure results in power and torque loss as well as higher fuel consumption and emission to the environment. This review paper aims to elucidate the relationship between exhaust backpressure and the performance of IC engine. Various past studies were conducted to study the effect of exhaust backpressure on the performance of IC engine through Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) simulation, engine simulation and experimental analysis. Some studies used Taguchi's method to optimize the exhaust manifold's design in respect to backpressure decrement. It was found that 0.22 kW to 0.45 kW of engine's power increases for every 1 kPa of exhaust backpressure decrement. At the same time, 1.5% to 3% of fuel consumption decreases for every 10 kPa of backpressure decrement. In contrast, higher backpressure does reduce the Nitrous Oxides (NO_x) emission in the exhaust gas due to higher temperature. Therefore, exhaust backpressure must be minimized to improve any IC engine's performance if the NO_x emission is neglected. This review paper is expected to provide a better understanding of the impact of exhaust backpressure on IC engine's performance.

III. Conclusion

Previous research has identified a number of elements that can be used to improve the overall performance of automobile mufflers. One typical method to boost performance in mufflers is to add surface area to the fluid transfer field inside the exhaust system. This element has increased the number of pathways for fluid to pass through the mufflers, increasing the process's efficiency. Noise reduction is also a prominent area of research. Mufflers are an important component when considering exhaust system of any automobile.

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